

Association of the Enthusiastic Drivers with Blood in Urine

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this current study was to determine the alliance of the nature of the driving lovers. The presence of blood in the urine is called Hematuria. It may be due to the infection of the kidney and bladder. The nature of the drivers is unique as compared to others. The nature put the element of an excitement in such type of people. It was concluded from this prompt study that there is no considerable alliance with the nature of the driving lovers and blood in urine.

Keywords: Hematuria, Driver lover's habits, Symptoms of hematuria, Causes of hematuria.

1. Introduction

The presence of blood in the urine is called Hematuria. There are two types of hematuria. First one is the gross hematuria and the second is microscopic hematuria. The gross hematuria is the condition in which blood can be seen in urine apparently while the microscopic hematuria is the condition in which blood in urine can only be seen through microscope. There are many reason of causing hematuria. It may be due to the infection of the kidney and bladder. Trauma and vigorous exercise are another reason of this but the main reasons of the hematuria are kidney or bladder cancer, inflammation of kidney and urethra, hemophilia and sickle cell disease. There are many symptoms of the hematuria. The urine of the people with gross hematuria is pink brown or red. Even the very little amount of the blood in urine alter the color of the urine. Apparently there are no other obvious symptoms of it except clot formation that cause the pain in back and bladder.

The nature of the drivers is unique as compared to others. Mainly there are two kinds of people. Some people are lazy in their nature and their laziness reflects in their habits. Some people are very active in their nature. Their activeness also reflects in their habits. Such type of people drives their vehicle at very fast speed. Such people are very fast and furious type. They always try to do their work swiftly as much as they can. The nature put the element of an excitement in such type of people. The scientific workers have already been correlate different parameters to the specific topic [1-10].

The main objective of this current study was to determine the alliance of the nature of the driver lovers with the blood in urine.

2. Materials and Methods

90 students took part in this job. All were the students of the Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Measurement of Blood in Urine

The urinalysis or the urine test was carried out of all the apprentices. The concentration of blood in the urine may be different. Anomalous quantity of blood in urine may due to viral infection or other disorders.

Study Design

A questioner was offered to shear his views about alliance of the nature of the driving lovers with the blood in urine.

Statistical Analysis

This study was operated with the help of Mini.tab.

3. Results and Discusion

Table 1. Association of nature of driving lovers with the blood in urine

Gender	Driving Likeness		Driving Dislikeness	
	Subsistence of blood in urine	No subsistence of blood in urine	Subsistence ce of blood in urine	No subsistence of blood in urine
Male	5	95	5	5
Female	8.5	75	2.8	11

The above results represented the valuable data about the presence and absence of blood in urine who liked to derive and also about those who deny of being driving lovers. In the male scholars of those who disclosed that they liked to drive were of 5 percent that contained blood in their urine and 95 percent of those that blood was not present in their urine. Similarly those scholars who have no interest in driving were only 5 percent that completely ensured about the absence of blood in their urine. In the case of female scholars only about 9 percent were those that have blood in their urine.

4. Conclusion

It was concluded from this prompt study that this prompt study that there is no considerable alliance with the nature of the driving lovers and blood in urine.

Declarations

Source of Funding

This research did not receive any grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare no competing financial, professional, or personal interests.

Ethical Approval

Ethical approval for this study was obtained from Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Bahauddin Zakariya University, Multan, Pakistan.

Consent for publication

The authors declare that they consented to the publication of this research work.

Availability of data and material

The authors are willing to share the data and material according to relevant needs.

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